

A milestone for TROLLing: 200 datasets published!

By Helene N. Andreassen, Philipp Konzett, Huw Haugland-Grange & Mara van der Ploeg, UiT The Arctic University of Norway

To mark the 200th dataset being archived and published in TROLLing, we asked the depositor of the dataset, **Georgia Knell** (Vrije Universiteit Brussel), about her experience of archiving data with TROLLing. We also provide some key stats about the archive and share our latest news.

TROLLing: a very short introduction

The Tromsø Repository for Language and Linguistics (TROLLing) is a curated discipline-specific data repository, hosting open data and code from linguistics researchers worldwide. TROLLing was launched on the Dataverse platform in 2014, and recent years have shown a steady increase in users and data deposits, with more and more researchers using TROLLing as the trustworthy home for data underpinning their scientific publications.

Dataset no. 200

Georgia Knell, PhD candidate at the Vrije Universiteit Brussel in Belgium, is the depositor of the 200th dataset and has agreed to answer some questions about her dataset and her research.

Georgia, can you tell us something about your research?

In my research I focus on a subset of different properties that have been theorised to affect saliency of L2 (second language) features in second language acquisition (SLA). Saliency refers to how noticeable or prominent a feature is to learners. My project is linked to **Saioa Cipitria's** project and we worked together on the [systematic review paper](#) linked to the dataset in question here. Together we designed five experiments using a semi-artificial language to isolate specific variables that could affect saliency. I find my project interesting because it combines linguistics with cognitive sciences, which are my two fields of study. This relationship with cognition in general is what makes saliency important.

Georgia Knell (left) and Saioa Cipitria (right) presenting a poster about saliency in SLA (photo: private)

Can you tell us more about your dataset?

The dataset belongs to the systematic review we conducted and published. There has been quite some research on the relationship between saliency and SLA and while there are many theories, there is a lack of empirical affirmation. The dataset contains the query results and annotations. We included articles focusing on empirical studies where saliency was treated as an independent variable. We annotated each article with detailed information on how it related to saliency, the properties it looked at, the type of saliency, the methodology used, the languages included, and the findings.

Why did you choose TROLLing?

Already early on in my project, it was clear that I wanted to practice open data. It was my supervisor **Ludovic de Cuypere** who suggested archiving and publishing our data in TROLLing.

Fun fact: Ludovic de Cuypere is part of 14 datasets in TROLLing!

How was your experience getting your dataset archived and published in TROLLing?

The process was quite smooth and straightforward. There was a bit of figuring out of the technical aspects at the beginning. The instructions provided were clear, which helped streamline the process. The TROLLing team was incredibly responsive, offering quick feedback and helpful suggestions for improvements. From start to finish, the process took around 2-3 weeks, the dataset was even published before the article. Having the data well-organized upfront definitely helped. I would say that having a clear Data Management Plan (DMP) made a big difference.

Do you have any recommendations for people who are thinking about archiving and publishing their dataset in TROLLing?

My biggest advice is to document everything as you go, not after the fact. It can be tedious, but it will save you time and stress later on. Be as detailed as possible when annotating, as others will not have the same familiarity with your research. It's easy to forget that someone coming from a different background or perspective might need more context than you might assume. So, the more detailed you can be, the better!

'The TROLLing team was incredibly responsive, offering quick feedback and helpful suggestions'

What do you hope is going to happen with your published dataset? (Or do you have any plans with it yourself?)

I know this dataset is very specific but if someone is doing similar research, I hope they are able to find the dataset and that it is useful for their work. If it can help a fellow researcher facilitate their work, then that is all that matters.

I regularly refer back to the dataset, especially when writing new papers. For instance, I'm currently working on a paper for the second experiment, and the dataset allows me to quickly look up which articles have examined particular properties related to salience. So, the dataset has also been really useful for me.

Georgia's datasets in TROLLing

Knell, Georgia; Cipitria, Saioa; De Cuypere, Ludovic; Housen, Alex; Struys, Esli, 2025, "Stand-out: A systematic review of the role of salience in second language acquisition", <https://doi.org/10.18710/EABCRW>, DataverseNO, V1

Knell, Georgia; De Cuypere, Ludovic; Manouilidou, Christina, 2024, "Method in the madness: Exploring factors that impact the processing of two-suffixed complex words", <https://doi.org/10.18710/R9IZSV>, DataverseNO, V1

We are particularly pleased to see early career researchers such as Georgia and Saioa embracing the recommended practice of depositing their research data in trustworthy repositories. This is not just a key step in making research data more [FAIR](#) but it also helps making scientific research more transparent and reproducible. In the long run, this can speed up scientific progress and build trust in society.

TROLLing data holdings per April 2025

When TROLLing celebrated its 10th year anniversary in 2024, two of our most regular users were interviewed in the UiT-based podcast Open Science Talk. In this episode, **Lukas Sönning** from the University of Bamberg and **Laura Janda** from UiT The Arctic University of Norway share their experiences. Their key message is how using a curated data repository has helped raise the quality of their own research by making it more transparent and reusable for others.

The anniversary episode can be accessed here: <https://doi.org/10.7557/19.7631>.

Lukas and Laura, and many others, have contributed to the increased amount of data in TROLLing. Data come from many subfields of linguistics, for instance phonetics, syntax, discourse analysis and morphology. Other examples are first and second language acquisition, sociolinguistics and revitalization.

‘Data come from many subfields of linguistics [...] in all shapes and sizes’

Every dataset includes a readme file as documentation, but otherwise they come in all shapes and sizes; some contain a single .csv file while others contain folders with zip files. Other recurring file types are sound files, text documents and code files.

Although datasets can be published without being linked to any research publication, most data in TROLLing are associated with a written work. Knowing how the publication process works in academia, we wish to make TROLLing a useful resource throughout that process. Two popular features we offer are getting a private URL to an unpublished dataset for sharing with editors and getting an anonymised version of the unpublished dataset to share with reviewers in the case of double-blind peer review.

TROLLing-related news and updates

We published [dataset no. 100](#) in early 2021, and since then, quite a few things have happened. Most importantly, we are in the middle of a process working on a future governance model for TROLLing, with key elements being operational sustainability and visibility in the user community, which will allow us to scale up our service in a user-centric, sound and trustworthy manner.

In this process, we are fortunate to receive advice from the TROLLing steering committee and the TROLLing scientific advisory board. These two bodies are composed of internationally recognised scholars with different types of expertise (see our [People page](#)), and are proving to be invaluable discussion partners at this defining stage in TROLLing's history.

Another positive development is that TROLLing has seen its curator team double from two to four. Being a discipline-specific repository, it is vital that we are up to date about needs and developments in our designated user communities, and by having more brains and people power, we are better equipped to do just that. In addition to continuously working on improving our curation services, we engage in both national and international networks, projects, and other communities that are relevant to our work. To mention but a few: The Linguistics Data IG of the Research Data Alliance, CLARIN – Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure, a national group on management of sensitive data, the EOSC EDEN & FIDELIS projects. In addition, we've received internal funding from UiT to work on a project entitled "Next-generation research infrastructure for language and linguistics: TROLLing 2030". More info to follow!

Want to learn more about our repository?

Visit the [repository](#) itself and our info website. [Contact](#) the curators. Follow us on LinkedIn. Talk with people who have already deposited data. Make depositing data in a trustworthy repository a discussion point with your colleagues and invite us in if we can be of use.